

Triterpenoids. XLIV. The Revised Structure of Barringtogenol B

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THE isolation of a number of triterpenoids from the various parts of the plant *Careya arborea* has been reported earlier¹⁻³. We report here the isolation of another triterpenoid sapogenol characterized as barringtogenol B for which a revised structure (Ia) is now proposed.

I

II a, R=H
b, R=Ac

III

The neutral aglycone fraction obtained by the acid hydrolysis of the crude glycosides isolated from the ethanolic extract of the leaves of *C. arborea* on column chromatography over silica gel furnished a sapogenol, called sapogenol A, $C_{35}H_{56}O_6$ (M^+ 572), m. p. $246^\circ-48^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D^{29} + 3.1^\circ$ (EtOH).

Sapogenol A yielded a triacetate (Id), $C_{41}H_{62}O_9$ (M^+ 698), m. p. $252^\circ-54^\circ$ on heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine on steam bath for 4 hr. Its IR spectrum showed a band at 3540 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of a hindered free OH group in the triacetate. Hydrogenation of sapogenol A in ethanol in presence of palladised charcoal (10%) catalyst furnished dihydrosapogenol A, $C_{35}H_{58}O_6$ (M^+ 574),

a m/e 207

b, m/e 364

m. p. $240^\circ-41^\circ$. The dihydroderivative still gave pale yellow coloration with tetranitromethane indicating the presence of one hindered double bond.

Sapogenol A showed absorption maximum at 212 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.09) which indicated the presence of an α, β -unsaturated ester group (angeloyloxy or tigloyloxy⁴) in sapogenol A. Dihydrosapogenol A showed absorption maximum at 208 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.6) indicating the presence of a trisubstituted double bond only. The IR spectrum of sapogenol A in Nujol mull showed absorption bands at 3450 cm^{-1} (-OH), 1700 cm^{-1} and 1645 cm^{-1} (for $>C=O$, $>C=C<$ respectively of an α, β -unsaturated ester function).

Saponification of sapogenol A with ethanolic KOH (10%) under reflux yielded a neutral triterpene alcohol and an acid. The triterpene alcohol, m. p. $314^\circ-19^\circ$, $C_{30}H_{50}O_5$ has been characterized as barringtogenol C⁵⁻⁷ (Ib) by comparison of mixed m. p., tlc and IR spectrum with an authentic sample. The acid fraction of the hydrolysate was identified as tiglic acid, m. p.

64°-65°, by comparison of m. p. and mixed m. p. with an authentic sample. But when the saponification was carried out with methanolic KOH (1N) at room temperature following the method of Bhattacharya *et al.*⁸, the acid fraction was identified as angelic acid, m. p. 44°-45°, by comparison of m. p. and mixed m. p. with an authentic sample. These data clearly showed that sapogenol A is a mono-angeloyl derivative of barringtogenol, C.

The mass spectrum of sapogenol A showed the molecular ion peak at m/e 572. It showed typical r. D. A fragmentation involving the 12 : 13 double bond⁹ giving rise to the ion species *a* (m/e 207) and *b* (m/e 364). The intensity of the peak at m/e 364 (ion *b*) was weak due to the loss of 100 mass units (angelic acid) from ion *b* leading to peak at m/e 264 which was very intense compared to ion *a*. The formation of the ion species *b*, obviously located the angeloyl moiety either in ring D or E of sapogenol A. There were also peaks at m/e 424 and 423 for the ions [M-angelic acid-H₂O-CH₂O]⁺ and [M-angelic acid-H₂O-CH₂OH]⁺ respectively. The loss of 30 (CH₂O) or 31 (CH₂OH) mass units during the formation of the above two ion species would eliminate the hydroxymethylene group at C-17 as the possible site for the angeloyl moiety in sapogenol A. This is further supported by the absence of any peak arising out of

the loss of 113 mass units (CH₂O.CO.C=CH) either from the molecular ion or from ion *b* in the mass spectrum of sapogenol A. By analogy with erythrodiol diacetate⁹, 113 mass units should have been eliminated from molecular ion as well as ion *b* if the angeloyl moiety was attached to the hydroxymethylene group at C-17 of sapogenol A. So the only remaining site for the angeloyl moiety in sapogenol A is C-16, C-22 or C-21. The C-16 axial α -OH in barringtogenol C is known to be highly hindered⁵, and sapogenol A has been found not to consume any periodic acid. So, most probably the angeloyloxy moiety in sapogenol A is linked to C-22 or C-21.

The mass spectrum of sapogenol A-triacetate (Id) showed the molecular ion peak at m/e 698. There were also peaks at m/e 249 and m/e 448, which clearly locates the hindered free OH gr. in the sapogenol A-triacetate in the D/E part of the molecule. The actual site for the free OH group is expected to be at C-16 because barringtogenol C is known to form tetraacetate in which the C-16 OH group remains free⁵.

Sapogenol A on treatment with dry acetone and anhydrous copper sulphate yielded mainly monoacetate (IIa), C₃₈H₆₀O₆ (M⁺ 612), m. p. 172°-75°, and another acetonide (III), C₃₈H₆₀O₆, m. p. 178°-82°, in very poor yield. The former one gave a monoacetate (IIb), C₄₀H₆₂O₇ (M⁺ 654), m. p. 222°-26°, on heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine on steam bath for 4 hrs which is in conformity with the structure (IIa) assigned to the acetonide. As expected the hindered

16 α -axial OH group was not acetylated. The mass spectrum of the monoacetate showed the molecular ion peak at m/e 654. The r. D. A. fragmentation gave rise to the peaks at m/e 249 and m/e 404 which clearly located the acetoxy group at C-3.

On the basis of the data so far discussed the structure of sapogenol A may be represented as (Ia).

Earlier we reported a compound called barringtogenol B¹⁰ from the fruits of *Barringtonia acutangula* Gaerth for which the structure (Ic) was proposed. The melting points of sapogenol A and its triacetate are very close to those reported for barringtogenol B (245°-47°) and its tetra-acetate* (248°-50°). Actually these were found to be identical with barringtogenol B and its tetra-acetate* respectively by comparison of m.p., mixed m.p., tlc and IR spectra. So the structure of barringtogenol B should be revised as (Ia).

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*The tetra-acetate reported earlier¹⁰ has now been found to be the triacetate (Id).